

**Light-powered liquid crystal polymer network actuator using TiO₂
nanoparticle as an inorganic UV-light absorber**

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Abstract: Recently design and fabrication of light-powered actuators have attracted intense attention because of the manufacturing of intelligent soft robots and innovative self-regulating devices. Accordingly, liquid crystal polymer network (LCN) provides a promising platform due to its reversible and multistimuli-responsive shape-changing behaviors. In particular, doping nanoparticles with exclusive properties into the LCN can produce interesting results. In this work, we investigated the TiO₂ nanoparticle-based LCN polymer light-powered actuator. TiO₂ nanoparticle as an inorganic ultraviolet (UV)-light absorber can substantially impact the LCN polymer's oscillatory behavior. Our results demonstrate that the oscillation characteristics are directly influenced by the presence of nanoparticles and we studied the influencing factors. The effectiveness of the elastic modulus, thermomechanical force, and curvature was investigated using different weight percentages of TiO₂ nanoparticles. Our results show that in the presence of TiO₂ nanoparticles, the polymer chain order and inter-chain interactions in the polymer matrix, as well as the structural deformation of relevant polymer surfaces, are changed.

Keywords: *liquid crystal, liquid crystal polymer network, light-powered actuator, nanoparticle, UV-light absorber*

1. Introduction

In today's world, the movement has penetrated everywhere in human life, which serves as the inspiration for modern industries.¹⁻³ Indeed, the oscillating movement has presented all of nature, such as leaves swinging with the breeze, birds flapping wings, ocean waves, and heartbeat, has attracted scientists' attention.^{2,4,5} In addition, oscillatory behaviors can be employed in practical applications such as soft robots and self-cleaning surfaces.⁶⁻⁸ Due to this appeal, many efforts have been devoted to designing and manufacturing self-oscillating actuators with self-determining movement in recent years.⁴⁻⁹ For this reason, crucial features such as enabling wireless, spatial and temporal control should be paid attention. Light can play a unique attribute in features of light-responsive soft actuators because it can be highly controllable in an untethered way with spatial and temporal accuracy.^{9,10}

For this reason, the use of light-sensitive materials is aimed in this work. Among different aspects of selecting the suitable material, the degree of flexibility and the capacity to change shape with a reasonable response time should be considered.^{11,12} These features help to overcome rigid actuator issues like finite freedom and relatively complex control systems.¹³ Liquid crystal polymer network (LCN), which combines the mechanical capabilities of polymers with the anisotropic nature of LC, has been prioritized as a candidate among the materials employed in this discipline. The LCN can produce controlled oscillating motions, and these materials have recently gained popularity for employment in mobile components. Moreover, they have sufficient elasticity and the capacity to alter shape against light irradiation.¹⁴⁻¹⁶

Recently, research in this field has been focused on increasing the scope of these lightpowered actuator applications. However, the integration of the exclusive properties of the LCN polymer with the appropriate dopant can provide the possibility of obtaining valuable results.^{17- 22}

Ultraviolet (UV)-light absorbers are one of the best candidates among the dopants. Due to having high energy of UV light and potentially breaking of intra- and intermolecular bonds and deteriorating the physical and chemical characteristics of LCN polymer, the UV light absorbers are a great selection and protect the actuator against UV-light radiation.²³⁻²⁶ For this reason, in this work, we fabricate a self-sustained oscillation of LCN polymer using organic UV-light absorbers and improve the photo-thermal effect of LCN polymer. Due to their superior performance over photo-chemical types in quick actuation and highly reversible responses with just one light wavelength, the emphasis is placed on photo-thermal effect-based actuators to accomplish this goal.²⁷

Inorganic UV-light absorbers are chosen because of their nontoxicity and high chemical stability.²⁸ One excellent choice among them is titanium dioxide (TiO_2), a chemically inert semiconducting substance that does not affect the nature of the host matrix.²⁹ Due to this substance's special characteristics, including its high refractive index, non-flammability, and high thermal capacity, a wide range of applications have been assigned to it, including wood coatings, solar cells, water purification systems, and cosmetics.³⁰⁻³³ Integrating the TiO_2 nanoparticles' exclusive properties with the LCN polymer's capabilities can produce exciting outcomes.

In this work, TiO_2 doped light-powered LCN polymer actuator was fabricated to explore the impact of stated nanoparticles on the oscillatory behavior. The oscillation characteristics under the influence of the weight percentage of nanoparticles were investigated as well. Moreover, different radiant polarizations, the effect of nanoparticles on chemical bonds in the polymer matrix using FT-IR spectroscopy, absorbance, molecular orientation with SEM images, and surface morphology by AFM technique were investigated. Indeed, by studying TiO_2 nanoparticles on the

resultant light-induced oscillatory behavior, we can get helpful information about the LCN polymer's elastic modulus, thermomechanical force, and curvature radius.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Materials

RM82 (Mw = 120000, Sigma Aldrich) and Irgacure369 (provided by Ciba, Basel, Switzerland) were used as nematic reactive mesogen and photo-initiator, respectively. Also, the silane-coated rutile TiO₂ nanoparticle (ssnano. Co. LTD) by an average size of 20 nm was selected as an inorganic UV-light absorber. Meanwhile, to carry out the studies as accurately as possible, used TiO₂ nanoparticles were mixed with Tinuvin460 (BASF) as an organic UV-light absorber which has already been studied,²⁵ in specific weight percentages as listed in Table. 1. It is also noteworthy that further, Polyimide X610-33C (JNC Corporation, Tokyo, Japan) and Polyimide SE-5662 (Nissan) were employed to create surface alignment layers with planar and homeotropic molecular orientation, respectively, to achieve splay molecular orientation in the LCN polymer matrix.

2.2. Polymerization

The photo-polymerization method was carried out for nine mixtures of the stated LCN with the same weight percentage of RM82 and Irgacure369 (96.5 wt% and 1 wt%, respectively). The weight percentage of Tinuvin460 and TiO₂ nanoparticles are variable, as listed in Table. 1, which are adjusted so that their sum equals 2.5 wt%. Because with the step-by-step increase in the weight percentage of TiO₂ nanoparticles, it is possible to examine their impact on the desired photoresponsive behavior more precisely. All mixtures were dissolved in dichloromethane (Merck

Co. Ltd) with the highest available purity. After ensuring the homogeneous mixing of nanoparticles and complete evaporation of dichloromethane by using a Laboratory Mixer (50 rpm 30 min 50 °C), the LC cells were filled with the remaining mixtures. In this way, the quartz sheets were coated using mentioned polyimides through the spin coating technique with the specified program: Program 1. 1200 rpm for 10 s; Program 2. 2000 rpm for 50 s. Then, the coated sheets were prebaked at 180 °C for 30 min. After finishing the coating step, to improve the orientation, micro-grooves are created on the planar alignment layer by rubbing on the velvet cloth. Subsequently, after gluing planar and homeotropic alignment sheets with UV glue with a set gap of 20 µm, the prepared cells are filled by the respective mixtures in the isotropic phase (110 °C) using the capillarity action. To complete the polymerization process, the mixture samples were exposed to 265 nm UV-light (power density 3.3 mW cm⁻²) for 35 minutes at the nematic phase of mixtures (92 °C). Finally, postcuring was done at 135 °C for 15 min.

Table. 1: Specified weight percentage (wt%) of Tinuvin460 and TiO₂ nanoparticles to polymerization of LCN polymer, within the polymerized films density.

LCN polymer	Tinuvin 460 (wt%)	TiO ₂ nanoparticles (wt%)	Density (kg/m ³)
LCN	2.5	0	1220
LCN/C-I	2.4	0.1	1223.1
LCN/C-II	2.2	0.3	1229.3
LCN/C-III	2	0.5	1235.5
LCN/C-IV	1.8	0.7	1241.7
LCN/C-V	1.5	1	1251
LCN/C-VI	1	1.5	1266.5

LCN/C-VII	0.5	2	1282
LCN/C-VIII	0	2.5	1297.5

3. Characterization

3.1. Characterization instruments

To study the physical and chemical characteristics of LCN polymer and examine the impact of utilized TiO₂ nanoparticles on the related polymer networks' chemical bonds, a Vertex 70 FT-IR spectrophotometer spanning the wavenumber range 400–4000 cm⁻¹ was used. Besides, checking molecular orientation in the polymer bulks is done by examining the images recorded by scanning electron microscopy, MIRA3 FEG-SEM. In addition, this microscope allows checking the dispersion of nanoparticles in the polymer matrix by energy dispersive X-ray mapping (EDX mapping) technique. To check the impact of utilized nanoparticles on the LCN polymer's morphology, a Nanosurf Mobile S device was used to conduct the atomic force microscope (AFM) study. To investigate the utilized nanoparticles' role on light absorbance, a double-beam Shimadzu UV-2450 UV-visible spectrophotometer spanning a wavelength range of 200–900 nm was used for obtaining UV-vis absorption spectra of samples. Meanwhile, ASTM/D638/Shimadzu testing machine was used to determine elastic modulus. Also, to record the temperature of the LCN polymer during oscillation, a Xenics Gobi thermal camera was used.

3.2. Adjusted experimental arrangement

To obtain the light-induced oscillating motion, polymerized LCN films are placed in the experimental setup, as shown in Figure. 1. It is very important to eliminate the factors causing

disturbances in the oscillatory behavior. Because we can investigate the impact of utilized TiO₂ nanoparticles on LCN behavior as precisely as possible. This was accomplished by selecting a radiant light source with a wavelength of 450 nm, which is outside the maximum absorption bands of TiO₂ and Tinuvin460 (see Figures. S1(a) and (b), in the supporting information). Further, a Fresnel rhomb (Newport) polarizer was used to adjust the light polarization direction. In this regard, the polymerized LCN films are all cut in a rectangular shape in the dimensions of 2 mm × 1.8 cm so that the generated grooves run parallel to the cantilever's long-axis direction. Then, sliced films are held in place by a clamp as the planar alignment surface is irradiated by the light source. Also, according to the exact dimensions of the films, their density was calculated after measuring their mass by a Sartorius MC 5 scale, and the obtained values are listed in the Table. 1. A 120 Hz frame rate video camera was used to record the resultant light-induced oscillating motions. Finally, using video analysis software (Tracker), the required parameters of the resultant oscillations were extracted from the collected images.

Figure 1. Experimental arrangement to achieve light-induced oscillating motion in the LCN films.

4. Result and discussion

4.1. Chemical and physical characteristics

To precisely analyze the LCN polymer's light-induced oscillatory behavior and controlling factors, the disturbance-causing factors should be considered. Thus, the following investigations were carried out on the physical and chemical characteristics of polymerized LCN films.

Firstly, the impact of TiO₂ nanoparticles on the chemical nature of LCN polymer was studied. To investigate this feature, the FT-IR spectra of all LCN films were recorded, and the spectrum associated with TiO₂-doped LCN films was compared to those related to non-doped LCN films. As shown in Figure. 2, the FT-IR spectrum of all films shows the same trend. Additionally, neither a new IR bond nor a change in the wavelength of the IR-active functional groups was observed. This indicates the failure of chemical bands between utilized nanoparticles and the LCN

polymer matrix.³⁴ This finding allows for the most precise execution of the appropriate research by guaranteeing the neutrality of the utilized TiO₂ nanoparticles.

Figure 2. FT-IR spectra of all LCN films.

By considering the significance of nanoparticle dispersion in the polymer matrix on its photoresponsive behavior,^{35, 36} the dispersion of the utilized nanoparticles was analyzed using the EDX-mapping technique. The dispersion of Titanium (Ti) in the corresponding polymer matrices

was examined for this aim. The related maps are shown in Figure. 3, which demonstrates that the specified element is homogenously distributed throughout the considered LCN polymer matrices. This presumes that the related dispersion in the polymer matrix with the highest weight percentage of TiO₂ nanoparticles (2.5 wt%) acquires disturbance. This suggests that when using significant weight percentages of nanoparticles, the aggregation will manifest itself. The pertinent findings, in turn, confirm the effectiveness of the photo-thermal effect in the considered polymer matrices from the dispersion of utilized TiO₂ nanoparticles. Additional related images are provided in supporting information (Figure. S2).

Figure 3. EDX-map from the dispersion of Ti in the number of LCN films: a) LCN/C-III, b) LCN/C-VIII

It should be noted that morphology is another influencing factor on the photo-responsive behavior of LCN polymer.^{25,37} SEM and AFM images of all LCN films' cross-sections and surfaces, respectively, were captured for this purpose. The analysis of images offers the chance to look into the influence of utilized nanoparticles on the splay molecular orientation in the considered polymer bulks. Because besides the molecular orientation's impact on the LCN polymer's photo-responsive behavior, the accomplishment of thermal anisotropy in the splay structures plays a significant role in the formation of photo-induced oscillating motion.³⁸ By contrasting the SEM images of the TiO₂-doped LCN films and the non-doped one, it is conceivable to identify the presence of the desired splay molecular homeotropic molecular orientation as present in all images. This finding, in turn, indicates orientation in the considered polymer bulks (see Figure. 4). Because the transfer from planar to the relevant molecular orientation is unaffected by utilized nanoparticles.

Figure 4. SEM images of all LCN films' cross section: a) LCN, b) LCN/C-I, c) LCN/C-II, d) LCN/C-III, e) LCN/C-IV, f) LCN/C-V, g) LCN/C-VI, h) LCN/C-VII, i) LCN/C-VIII. The top and bottom surfaces are planar and homeotropic oriented, respectively.

Subsequently, AFM images of all polymer surfaces were captured, including both planar and homeotropic molecular orientations. The images of non-doped LCN and LCN/C-VIII are given in Figure. 5, and the images related to the rest of the TiO_2 -doped films are presented in supporting information (see Figure. S3). In this regard, the non-uniformity of the respective polymer surfaces' roughness is revealed by comparing the related roughness of the TiO_2 -doped LCN films with the

non-doped LCN film. Even though the planar and homeotropic-oriented surface roughness (Sa_{\parallel} and Sa_{\perp}) are not the same in all of them, the surface roughness in the TiO_2 -doped films has decreased in comparison to the non-doped LCN. This result expresses the influence of TiO_2 nanoparticles on the LCN chain structural tension of relevant polymer surfaces. Because the molecular orientations are not the same on the side surfaces of the considered LCN films, the surface roughness ratio ($Sa_{\perp}/Sa_{\parallel}$) was calculated in order to provide the possibility of investigate accurately. The values listed in Table. 2, show that the specified ratio decreases when utilized nanoparticles are present. While the surface roughness ratio of TiO_2 -doped films rises as the weight percentage of nanoparticles does. In this manner, it appears that an increase in the pertinent weight percentage has a more significant impact on the structural chain tension in the planar oriented LCN layer than the homeotropic oriented one.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. AFM images of planar (images on the left) and homeotropic (images on the right) oriented surfaces: a) LCN, b) LCN/C-VIII.

Subsequently, according to the influence of light absorbance on the effectiveness of the photothermal effect in the LCN polymer, the absorption spectrum of all the LCN films was recorded as shown in Fig 6. For this purpose, the relevant spectrums at the 450 nm wavelength, which is the light wavelength, were investigated. Next, to investigate as precisely as feasible, the absorption coefficient (β) of all films in this wavelength was determined through Beer-Lambert's law.³⁹ As listed in Table. 2, the results demonstrate a decrease in the related coefficient in the presence of TiO₂ nanoparticles. It is noteworthy that the values calculated for the LCN films, are the same in all the considered polarizations to investigate the oscillatory behavior, separately. Additionally, in the TiO₂-doped films, the absorption coefficient drops as the weight percentage of nanoparticles rises. Regarding the operation of TiO₂ as a UV-light protector, the resultant declining tendency can confirm the increased light scattering in the LCN films with a higher percentage of TiO₂ dopant.

Figure 6. UV-vis absorption spectrum of all LCN films.

Table. 2: Surface roughness ratio ($S_{a\perp}/S_{a\parallel}$) and absorption coefficient (β) at the radiation wavelength (450 nm) of the LCN films.

Polymer Film	$S_{a\perp}/S_{a\parallel}$	β (1/cm)
LCN	1.88	39.61
LCN/C-I	1.34	26.41
LCN/C-II	1.36	25.15
LCN/C-III	1.39	17.45
LCN/C-IV	1.41	14.07
LCN/C-V	1.46	8.12

LCN/C-VI	1.51	7.92
LCN/C-VII	1.57	7.31
LCN/C-VIII	1.65	5.18

4.2. Oscillation characteristics

To achieve light-induced oscillating motion, all films were arranged in the experimental setup, as shown in Figure. 1. Then, we studied the influencing factors on the oscillatory behavior of LCN films based on their chemical and physical characteristics. For this purpose, all films were attached to the clip so that the place of light radiation was about 2 mm lower than the attachment point, known as the hinge point. In this regard, all the films started to oscillate after bending toward the light source. Every obtained oscillation persisted without interruption, and the oscillatory behavior of all the films was recorded in the same way for 60 minutes by the 120 Hz frame video camera incorporated into the experimental arrangement to explore their characteristics as precisely as possible. To progress the relevant investigations, all films were exposed to radiant light with polarizations of 0° (parallel), 45° , and 90° (perpendicular), respectively. The corresponding polarizations are established according to the orientation of the cantilever's long axis concerning the radiant light source. The existence of structural anisotropy in the corresponding LCN network, which is the result of the presence of splay molecular orientation, in turn, causes the nonuniformity of the LCN polymer's oscillatory behavior with different polarizations of radiant light.⁴⁰

For advancing the relevant investigations, by reviewing the recorded videos, all oscillation characteristics were extracted by Tracker software and then determined by the sinusoidal fitting procedure. The findings of the proper examinations revealed that during the recording period, all

oscillations were consistently stable in consistent amplitude and frequency and continued to occur without any flaws. However, the pattern of resulting oscillations for equal 10 seconds is given in Figure. 7, and the relevant characteristics are listed in the Table. 3. Notably that the non-doped LCN's oscillation frequency is high compared to the TiO₂-doped types, to show the corresponding oscillation pattern as clearly as possible, its pattern is drawn for 1 second. Additional related oscillation patterns are provided in supporting information (Figures. S4(a) to (h)).

Figure 7. Oscillation pattern with irradiation of polarized light: a) LCN with all polarizations, b) parallel polarization, c) 45° polarization, d) perpendicular polarization. Temperature changes between LCN films' surfaces with increasing weight percentage of TiO₂ nanoparticles: 1- 0.5 °C.

Table 3. Oscillation frequency (f) and amplitude (A) during irradiation with polarized light, and also their frequency rate (f_{\perp}/f_{\parallel}).

	Frequency (Hz)			Amplitude (mm)			f_{\perp}/f_{\parallel}
	0° (parallel)	45°	90° (perpendicular)	0° (parallel)	45°	90° (perpendicular)	
LCN	10.04	11.023	8.95	1.236	1.311	1.728	0.891
LCN/C-I	1.58	0.935	0.465	0.032	0.065	0.096	0.294
LCN/C-II	1.319	0.755	0.433	0.041	0.091	0.145	0.328
LCN/C-III	1.11	0.577	0.382	0.07	0.1	0.147	0.344

LCN/C-IV	0.997	0.497	0.346	0.088	0.112	0.165	0.347
LCN/C-V	0.937	0.435	0.326	0.102	0.127	0.168	0.348
LCN/C-VI	0.911	0.427	0.319	0.112	0.135	0.186	0.350
LCN/C-VII	0.908	0.369	0.32	0.129	0.144	0.199	0.352
LCN/C-VIII	0.901	0.323	0.318	0.136	0.145	0.209	0.353

As can be seen, the oscillatory behavior of the LCN polymer is directly influenced by TiO₂ nanoparticles. The amplitude and frequency of the oscillations of the LCN polymer are significantly reduced by the presence of a TiO₂ dopant. Thus, in all oscillations, the highest and lowest oscillation frequency is obtained when all LCN films are exposed to light with parallel and perpendicular polarization, respectively (see Figure. 8). In this regard, it is determined that along with the reduction of oscillation characteristics in the presence of TiO₂ nanoparticles, the oscillation frequency reduces along with the increase in the weight percentage of nanoparticles by comparing the findings obtained for the TiO₂-doped films. To better analyze, the frequency rate of all resultant oscillations (f_{\perp}/f_{\parallel}) was calculated, and the values are listed in Table. 3. The f_{\perp}/f_{\parallel} values show a considerable decrease in the corresponding ratio when the LCN polymer is doped with TiO₂ nanoparticles. This result shows a high difference between oscillation frequency values with perpendicular and parallel polarized radiant light in the non-doped LCN film. Additionally, in the TiO₂-doped LCN films, increasing the corresponding ratio is obtained simultaneously with the increase in the weight percentage of nanoparticles. Thus, LCN/C-I and LCN/C-VIII have the lowest and highest f_{\perp}/f_{\parallel} values, respectively.

Figure 8. Oscillation frequency of all LCN films during irradiation with polarized light.

However, to produce the most accurate and correct analyses relating to the oscillatory behavior of the LCN polymer, looking into the influencing aspects is highly needed. Following the extensive previous studies, it has been determined that the oscillation frequency depends on the influencing factors as shown in the following equation:⁴¹

$$f = \frac{\alpha^2}{2\pi L^2} \sqrt{\frac{EI}{\rho D}} \quad (1)$$

The values of α , L , I , and D , which express the oscillation mode constant, cantilever length, moment of inertia, and area of the cross-section, respectively, in all LCN films, are the same because their oscillation mode and dimensions are the same. Thus, the variable factors in the present study are the elastic modulus (E) and the density (ρ) of the films. By knowing the values of all the given variables, it is possible to determine the elastic modulus of the LCN polymer. For

this reason, the elastic modulus of all LCN films was determined by substituting the values of all the components mentioned earlier with their density and oscillation frequency provided in Tables. 2 and 3, respectively. It should be emphasized that by taking into consideration the oscillation frequencies with 45° polarized radiant light, these calculations were made. Because according to Malus's law,⁴² all oriented layers in the polymer bulk contribute to the absorption of radiation light with the mentioned polarization. The results of the calculations are provided in Table. 4, which demonstrates the impact of utilized nanoparticles in reducing the elastic modulus of LCN polymer. Therefore, the elastic modulus of TiO₂-doped LCN films is substantially lower than the non-doped film. This is while the elastic modulus of TiO₂-doped LCN films decreases as the weight percentage of the nanoparticles increases. Thus, the highest and lowest elastic modulus of TiO₂-doped LCN films belongs to LCN/C-I and LCN/C-VIII, respectively. The elastic modulus of all LCN films persuades us to experimentally investigate the execution of additional investigation. Particularly, the relevant measurements were carried out at a certain temperature similar to the hinge point of the films during oscillation (about 57 °C). As listed in Table. 4, the values obtained using the two indicated methodologies show the same changing trend, with the measured values being greater than the calculated ones. The discrepancy in the measured values is caused by the non-uniformity of the stress imposed on the LCN films under the experimental measurement conditions of applying homogenous heat and the heat created as a result of the photothermal effect when the films are exposed to light. In this approach, subjecting the film to the light source's radiation puts it under more stress. It is important to note that the elastic modulus of the LCN polymer increases in the case of obtaining a chemical bond between the utilized nanoparticles and the polymer network or strengthening the inter-chain interaction in the polymer matrix.⁴³ The result shows that in the TiO₂-doped LCN, the effective interaction between the LCN polymer

chains decreases. It makes sense to obtain a lowering trend in the TiO₂-doped LCNs' elastic modulus, given the absence of a new band in the FT-IR spectrum. This supports the weakened inter-chain interactions in the LCN polymer matrix in the presence of TiO₂ nanoparticles. As a result, variations in the elastic modulus of the LCN films lead to the previously described variations in oscillation frequencies.

Table. 4: Elastic modulus (MPa) derived from two methodologies: experimental and equational.

Polymer Film	Calculated elastic modulus (MPa)	Measured elastic modulus (MPa)
LCN	406	605
LCN/C-I	4.05	5.35
LCN/C-II	2.65	3.46
LCN/C-III	1.56	2.13
LCN/C-IV	1.16	1.69
LCN/C-V	0.90	1.39
LCN/C-VI	0.87	1.21
LCN/C-VII	0.66	0.98
LCN/C-VIII	0.61	0.91

In addition to the findings mentioned above, it is crucial to consider how nanoparticles affect thermo-mechanical force to achieve oscillatory behavior. Because of the contraction of the planar alignment surface and the expansion of the homeotropic alignment surface, this force causes

oscillating motion in the cantilever by generating torque. The relevant force can be calculated through the following equation:⁴⁴

$$F = 6AEI/L^3 \quad (2)$$

Where A , E , I , and L are the oscillation amplitude, elastic modulus, a moment of inertia, and the length of the studied films, respectively. It is noteworthy that for this purpose, the values of the calculated elastic modulus were used because it is important to be influenced by the experimental conditions to achieve the oscillating movement. Due to the distinct alignment on each surface of LCNs, the different impacts are predictable for light polarization on their oscillatory behavior. To make a more accurate comparison possible, the thermomechanical force rate (F_{\perp}/F_{\parallel}) was calculated. The results of these calculations, which are drawn in Figure. 9, indicate a significant reduction in the related rate when LCN polymer was doped with TiO_2 nanoparticles. Additionally, in TiO_2 -doped LCN films, the corresponding rate falls as the weight percentage of nanoparticles rises. This, in turn, illustrates the impact of TiO_2 nanoparticles on the contraction and expansion of the polymer layers and surfaces in response to light exposure.⁴⁵

Figure 9. Thermomechanical force rate (F_{\perp}/F_{\parallel}) of all LCN films.

The effectiveness of the oscillation amplitude in the presence of TiO_2 nanoparticles shown in Table. 3, where a considerable reduction in the oscillation amplitude of the LCN polymer in the presence of TiO_2 nanoparticles has been observed. As known, doping the LCN polymer with TiO_2 nanoparticles causes a disturbance in the orientation of LCN chains. Thus, it affects the contraction and expansion of LCN polymer bulk and surface. The reduction of related oscillation amplitude in the TiO_2 -doped LCN films, with the increase in the nanoparticle's weight percentage, was observed. Because in such conditions, the nanoparticles increase the ordering of polymer chains and amplitude. These findings and the surface roughness rates are shown in Table. 2. This indicates the influence of TiO_2 nanoparticles on the LCN polymer's available surface for bending, which directly affects oscillation amplitude. The high surface roughness ratio is the expression of the more available surface which subsequently leads to an increase in the oscillation amplitude. As

shown in Figure. 10, the resultant oscillation amplitude in all polarized light increases in TiO₂-doped LCN films with the increase in the weight percentage dopant.

Figure 10. Oscillation amplitude of LCN films with irradiation of polarized light.

It is essential to note that a hypothetical circle is formed around the polymerized films due to the change of their shape from flat to curve during oscillation. To analyze the impact of the nanoparticles on the created curvature, the change in the radius of these hypothetical circles was investigated. The curvature radius (R) can be carried out through Eq. (3):⁴⁴

$$R = L^2 / 6A \quad (3)$$

Where L and A are the length of the studied films and the oscillation amplitude, respectively. The obtained results are depicted in Figure. 11, which indicates a rise in the corresponding radius when the LCN polymer is doped with TiO₂ nanoparticles. In addition, with the increase in the weight percentage of nanoparticles, there is a decreasing trend in the TiO₂-doped LCN films. As written

in Eq. (3), the oscillation amplitudes impact the related radius values. Because the lowest amplitude belongs to LCN/C-I, its radius is more than that of all LCN films. Therefore, the hypothetical circle shrinks as the oscillation amplitude increases along with the increase of associated curvature.

Figure 11. Curvature radius of all LCN films.

5. Conclusion

In this work, a light-powered actuator was fabricated by using UV-light absorbers. To fabricate a light-powered LCN polymer actuator, we used TiO_2 nanoparticles as an inorganic UV-light absorber due to their great chemical stability and low toxicity. Investigations into the effect of TiO_2 nanoparticles on the LCN polymer's oscillation behavior were done after establishing

nanoparticles' neutrality, lack of impact on the splay molecular orientation in the polymer bulk, and homogenous dispersion in the polymer matrix. A significant decrease in the LCN polymer's elastic modulus was observed by determining the elastic modulus of all LCN films. Our results showed that TiO₂ nanoparticle with different weight percentages affects the LCN polymer's oscillatory behavior, where the oscillation characteristics of TiO₂-doped LCN films were significantly less than the non-doped film. This reveals the strength of the influencing factors in this behavior. In such a way, by looking at thermo-mechanical force values, it turned out that TiO₂ nanoparticles had an impact on polymer bulk and surfaces' contraction and expansion to produce oscillating motion. This is due to their existence altering the LCN inter-chain ordering, which was discovered by varying oscillation amplitude. In addition, it was found that the curvature radius changed due to the presence of the TiO₂ nanoparticles and the alteration of their weight percentage. Finally, it can be said that in the applications of TiO₂ nanoparticles where oscillation is necessary to prevent the polymer surfaces from being deactivated, the doped LCN with TiO₂ nanoparticles can be used and can achieve the desired oscillation with the amount of doping. LCN doped with TiO₂ nanoparticles can be used for soft robotic systems from hardware for powering and control.

Supporting Information

- Details of the results obtained from UV-vis spectrum, EDX mapping, AFM images and light-induced self-oscillation studies. This material is available free of charge via the internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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Notes

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